

Boosting GPGPU virtualization and multiplexing with RDMA communication

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Abstract. Hardware virtualization is essential in High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Cloud Computing. It addresses resource allocation challenges, scalability, and performance isolation in shared environments. With the rise of GPGPU-accelerated HPC clusters, research has increasingly focused on GPGPU virtualization, leading to various solutions. This work explores the Generalized Virtualization Service (GVirtuS), a transparent virtualization solution with a plug-in framework for easy development and choice of communicators and stub libraries. We discuss GVirtuS' implementation and design choices and compare them with similar solutions. Additionally, we show how GVirtuS' performance was enhanced with a novel RDMA-based communicator, evaluated through CUDA implementations of SAXPY and Matrix Multiplication. Our RDMA Communicator achieved a 35% performance boost over the TCP Communicator on Infiniband and a 55% boost over TCP on Ethernet.

Keywords: GPU · Virtualization · Multiplexing · RDMA

1 Introduction

GVirtuS enables GPGPU sharing, multiplexing and virtualization offering a technology-agnostic, plug-in-style framework for various acceleration and communication libraries. GVirtuS uses a modular approach for data transmission, initially implementing a TCP/IP Communicator. However, TCP/IP's performance in GPGPU remoting is limited due to numerous context switches and data copies. This paper presents a novel approach using Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) for CUDA kernel offloading. RDMA enables data transmission without system calls, reducing context switches. Coupled with Infiniband, RDMA offers data transfer rates up to 400Gb/s and ultra-low latency. This work details the design, implementation, and evaluation of an RDMA over Infiniband Communicator for GVirtuS, tested with Matrix Multiplication and SAXPY algorithms.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows: in Section 2, we describe both related work to GVirtuS and other RDMA Communicator implementation

attempts; in Section 3 and Section 4 we present how the RDMA over Infiniband Communicator was designed and implemented; in Section 5 we analyze the benchmarks of the Communicator and in Section 6 we draw some conclusions, with a brief discussion about what gone wrong and what not, and the future developments.

2 Related work

The efficiency of GPGPUs for scientific computing applications and the rise of cloud computing have led to several research studies in GPGPU remote computing. In particular, two research projects relied on similar GPU virtualization solutions to GVirtuS: rCUDA [4][6] and Distributed-Shared CUDA (DS-CUDA) [3]. These works use a similar approach to GVirtuS: they provide CUDA API wrappers to the front end to intercept calls to CUDA functions and offload the execution on a remote GPGPU. Even if the goal is the same, these three works differ in some aspects:

- GVirtuS does provide a transparent virtualization solution. Recompiling the CUDA Application’s source code would only be helpful if the latter were compiled with CUDA-shared libraries. In contrast, DS-CUDA needs re-compilation.
- GVirtuS provides a plug-in and vendor-agnostic architecture, with easy-to-implement modules. In contrast, DS-CUDA and rCUDA only work within the Nvidia ecosystem. In addition, GVirtuS provides an hypervisor and technology agnostic communicator interface. In contrast, rCUDA and DS-CUDA only provide Infiniband and TCP socket communication.
- GVirtuS and DS-CUDA are open-source, while rCUDA is closed source.

Other noteworthy projects are vCUDA [5], and GVIM [2]. vCUDA implements a client-server model consisting of three user space modules. The first is the "vCUDA library," which resides in the guest and is a substitute for the original libcuda. It works like the GVirtuS Cuda STUB library, intercepting and redirecting CUDA API calls. The second module is the so-called "vCUDA STUB library". This module resides in the host OS, and its purpose is to receive and execute the remote requests made by the guest OS. The third module is the "vGPU". The vCUDA library uses it, and it provides some abstraction and synchronization functionalities. GVIM is an Xen-based solution for virtualizing GPGPUs, that exploits a split-driver approach similar to GVirtuS. It offers efficient accelerator virtualization, but its deployment requires some modification to the guest VMs running on the virtualized HPC platform. The split-driver model and an Infiniband-based connection are familiar to the GPGPU virtualization landscape. While GVirtuS leverages the split-driver model, it is not "RDMA over Infiniband ready" yet. That’s the purpose of this work.

A student from Virginia Tech already attempted to implement an RDMA Communicator in GVirtuS, leveraging RDMA over Converged Ethernet (ROcE) technology to perform the data transmission between the front-end and back-end

modules of GVirtuS. Their RDMA Communicator decreased execution times of a matrix multiplication algorithm by 12% to even 50%³. There are some differences in our work:

- **Optimizations:** Both our work and Virginia Tech’s work rely on memory region preregistration since it’s a hidden cost of RDMA that could (and did, more on that in Section 5) remove any performance advantage of using RDMA and Infiniband. We also rely on polling-based work completion instead of event-based work completion. In addition, Virginia Tech’s communicator also relies on cache-aligning the buffers, RDMA-receive pre-posting (or so-called mailbox approach), pipelined and batched network transfers and interception of CUDA memory management function calls. We didn’t implement this kind of optimization in our code since the scope of our work is to develop a straightforward way to transmit data between the front and back end.
- **Testing:** While both works share the idea of using RDMA to perform data transmission, our work aims to exploit the entire Infiniband infrastructure. We tested our communicator on an Infiniband network, while Virginia Tech’s communicator was tested only on Ethernet networks.

3 Design

One of the strengths of GVirtuS is its modularity. New plug-ins and components can be quickly developed because of GVirtuS’s modular nature. When it comes to communicator development, GVirtuS provides a crucial tool: the Communicator Interface. This interface exposes all the necessary methods for a communicator to be compatible with GVirtuS, serving as a bridge between the application and the GVirtuS system (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Communicator Interface of GVirtuS

These methods are:

- **Serve:** Sets the communicator as a server;

³ <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/items/447ddaef-8852-481f-92c3-905943f3f0eb>

- **Accept**: Accepts an incoming connection and returns the Communicator associated with it;
- **Connect**: Sets the Communicator as a client and tries to connect to an endpoint;
- **Read**: Simply reads the data sent from the peer;
- **Write**: Simply sends data to the peer;
- **Sync**: Actually useful in stream based communicators. It is used to flush communication streams. If no streams are used, the method is expected to do nothing;
- **Close**: Closes the connection with the endpoint;
- **to_string**: Returns a string representing the Communicator.

Fig. 2: Communicator Interface flow

The Communicator methods follow a specific sequence. A simple RDMA Server application programmed with the GVirtuS communicator interface should at least perform the following operations:

1. Instantiate a new communicator;
2. Put the newly instantiated Communicator in server mode using the Serve method in order to allow it to listen to incoming connection requests;
3. Accept an incoming connection request with the Accept method and save the Communicator returned by this method. The new Communicator will be used to handle the communication;
4. Perform data transmission using the Read method to get data and the Send method to send data;
5. Use the Close method to end the communication.

Likewise, a simple RDMA client programmed with the GVirtuS communicator interface should perform at least the following operations:

1. Instantiate a new communicator;
2. Initiate a new connection with the Connect method;
3. Perform data transmission Read method to get data and Send method to send data;
4. Use the Close method to end the communication.

Thanks to the Communicator Interface, designing an RDMA Communicator is therefore easy, since the new RDMACommunicator class should just extend the interface (Fig. 3). This module will be loaded at runtime.

Fig. 3: Implementation of GVirtuS communicator interface

The user can choose which Communicator to use by editing the properties.json file, will be read and parsed by GVirtuS. Two Factory classes will then cooperate to load the actual Communicator. We needed to add our Communicator into the factory classes. The actual operation flow for loading a communicator is the following:

1. GVirtuS reads the properties.json file;
2. The file is passed to an Endpoint Factory class. This class will instantiate and return the actual endpoint;
3. The endpoint is then passed to a Communicator Factory class. This class will dynamically load the correct communicator library based on the endpoint information provided.

As can be seen, to load the Communicator at runtime, another component needs to be developed: the Endpoint RDMA Class. This class will represent the endpoint property and carry the information from the properties.json file we just discussed. GVirtuS provides an Endpoint interface, too, so developing such a class was easy since we only needed to implement the interface.

4 Implementation

The RDMA over Infiniband communicator discussed in this work was implemented as a C++ class. In particular, as mentioned in Section 3, the RDMACommunicator class implements the Communicator interface. Therefore, we had

to implement the Serve, Accept, Connect, Read, Write, and Sync methods. We also had to add other attributes to hold necessary and valuable data. These attributes are two `rdma_cm_id` pointers to hold the RDMA Communication Managers used to represent the connection, two C-style strings holding the host-name and port, an `ibv_wc` field to hold the Work Completion used for checking if a send or receive operation is completed and an `ibv_mr` pointer to register the input/output buffers for messaging. Now, we will look at how we implemented the Read and Write methods for the first time. We disclose that these implementations have horrible performance because the hidden costs aren't optimized yet.

The Read method transmits data by receiving peer data and writing it into a buffer. Unlike TCP sockets, RDMA does not use streams, so this method was developed accordingly. The Verbs API offers one-sided (RDMA Read/Write) and two-sided (RDMA Send/Recv) primitives. Since GVirtuS uses two-sided communication, we chose RDMA Send and Recv for straightforward synchronous communication. The Recv primitive, equivalent to the read system call, posts a Recv Work Request to the Receive Queue of a Queue Pair without relying on system calls or context switches.

Fig. 4: Unoptimized RDMA Communicator Read flow

Fig. 5: Unoptimized RDMA Communicator Write flow

To post a Recv Work Request using `rdma-cm` verbs, you need to provide an `rdma_cm_id`, a buffer for the data, the buffer's size, and a registered memory region. Registering this memory region involves the kernel and causes a context switch, which impacts efficiency. The `ibv_poll_cq` function synchronizes and waits for the Recv Request to complete by polling Work Completions from a

Completion Queue. This function is called in a loop until a Work Completion is read.

The Write method is the other method that performs data transmission. Its purpose is to send data to the receiver side of the connection. It leverages the Send verb primitive. The Write method works in the same way as the Read one:

1. Registers a Memory Region associated with the input buffer passed as a parameter;
2. Posts a Send Work Request;
3. Waits for the Work Completion;

As previously mentioned, the RDMA technology can provide excellent data transmission performances thanks to its design. However, its hidden costs could make the performances even worse than TCP/IP.

The main hidden cost of RDMA is the "use of control operations in the data path." The verbs API provides two types of operations: data operations and control operations. Data operations, which send and receive data and confirm these actions, are optimized to avoid context switches. Control operations, such as create, destroy, modify, and query, are expensive because they cause context switches and use dynamic memory. Therefore, control operations should be avoided in the data path. The following sections will explain the importance of this insight.

The RDMA device requires a memory region associated with the buffer for send and receive operations, which must be registered beforehand. This memory registration is expensive. Initially, we registered the memory region before each send or receive call, resulting in poor performance, even worse than TCP/IP. To improve this, we now pre-register the memory region and reuse the same buffer repeatedly. We use a fixed-size buffer, avoiding memory registration for data that fits. For larger data, we register a new memory region specifically for that transmission. The following pseudocode shows how this mechanism works:

Listing 1.1: Pseudocode about the usage of Preregistered Buffers in RDMA Communication

```

let buf be the buffer used in the transmission
let size be the size of the transmission
let thresh be the size of the pre-registered buffer
let prereg_buf be the pre-registered buffer
let prereg_mr be the pre-registered memory region

IF size < thresh
  Send
    copy buf into prereg_buf
  send/recv(prereg_buf, prereg_mr, size)
  wait for completion
  IF recv
    copy prereg_buf into buf
ELSE
```

```

    let be a newly allocated memory region associated with buf
    send/recv(buf, mr, size)
    wait for completion

```

```

IF size > thresh
    deregister mr

```

According to [1], copying data into a pre-registered buffer is less expensive than registering a new memory region for small buffers. This optimization significantly improved performance by avoiding numerous context switches during memory registration.

We opted for polling-based work completion over events-based to lower latency despite increased CPU usage. Given the real-time nature of virtualization, the trade-off for reduced latency was deemed worthwhile.

Lastly, we set the queue pair's `min_rnr_timer` field to 0.01 milliseconds, the lowest allowed value. This minimizes latency during data retransmission, avoiding delays when one peer posts a send request before the other posts a receive request. As discussed in Section 5, these optimizations are the key to fast RDMA communication. Consequently, we had to tune and tweak some things in the RDMA Communicator class and the Read and Write methods to perform well. We added a Pre-registered Buffer of 5 Kilobytes and a Pre-registered Memory Region attribute to be registered for messaging before any Read or Write method is called.

Once an instance of the Communicator is created, it could be in client or serving mode. The RDMA Communicator class uses the `Serve` method to set the Communicator as a Server and allow it to listen for incoming connections. The `Serve` function performs the following operations:

1. Allocates a `rdma_addrinfo` struct to hold the hints of services the caller supports. We initialize the `ai_port_space` field to `RDMA_PS_IB` and `ai_flags` to `RAI_PASSIVE` to indicate that it supports Infiniband port space and that it is the passive side of the connection;
2. Uses the `rdma_addrinfo` function to resolve the destination host and port and returns information needed to establish communication;
3. Allocates an `ibv_qp_init_attr` struct to hold the initial attributes of the Queue Pair that is about to be created. The QP type will be set to Reliable Connection (RC).
4. It initializes the Queue Pair and calls the `rdma_listen` function to wait for incoming connections.

After all these operations, the Communicator is now set as a server and listens to incoming connections. This method must be called before the `Accept` method.

Once the Communicator is set as a server and is actively listening for connections, it should be able to accept any connection request. To make this possible, we implement the `Accept` method. This method is simple: it just calls the `rdma_get_request` function to retrieve a connection request event, and then it

calls the `rdma_accept` function to establish the connection finally. Before returning a new RDMA Communicator instance to handle the connection, it sets the `min_rnr_timer` Queue Pair Attribute to the lowest value possible.

The client counterpart of the `Serve` and `Accept` methods is the `Connect` method. This method will be used on the client side to initiate a connection request to a remote destination. The `Connect` method performs the same operations as the `Serve` and `Accept` methods, with just some small tweaks and additions:

1. Allocates a `rdma_addrinfo` struct to hold the hints of services the caller supports. We initialize the `ai_port_space` field to `RDMA_PS_IB`, but this time, we do not set the `ai_flags` to `RAI_PASSIVE`. With these tunings, we are indicating that the Communicator supports Infiniband port space and that it is the active side of the connection;
2. Uses the `rdma_addrinfo` function to resolve the destination host and port and returns information needed to establish communication;
3. Allocates an `ibv_qp_init_attr` struct to hold the initial attributes of the Queue Pair that is about to be created. The values are the same as those used for the `Serve` method;
4. It initializes the Queue Pair and calls the `rdma_connect` function to request a remote destination connection.
5. Once the connection is established, it sets the `min_rnr_timer` Queue Pair Attribute to the lowest value possible;
6. Before finally returning, it performs the buffer and memory region pre-registration.

We previously reviewed the unoptimized `Read` implementation. Here is how we optimized it: We pre-registered the memory region before `Read` (or `Write`) calls to avoid context switches. If the output buffer is smaller than the pre-registered buffer, we read the data into it and use `memcpy` to copy it to the output buffer. If the output buffer is more prominent than the pre-registered buffer, we register a new Memory Region and read the data directly, eliminating the need for copying.

The `getString` function is crucial for `GVirtuS` data transmission and closely relates to the `Read` method. Used by the `Process` class to read a string from the peer (usually a CUDA function symbol), we had to modify it for compatibility with our Communicator. The original version read one char at a time from a socket stream using the `TCPCommunicator`'s `Read` method. Since RDMA does not use streams, we used the `to_string` method to identify the Communicator type. For `RDMACommunicator`, `getString` reads 30 characters at a time, appends them to the output string, and returns. This size worked for our tests but can be adjusted as needed.

We optimized the `Write` method similarly to the `Read` method. Now, it only dynamically allocates a buffer if the input buffer is larger than the pre-registered one. Since the pre-registered buffer is allocated in advance, this avoids additional system calls.

Fig. 6: Optimized RDMA Communicator Read flow

Fig. 7: Optimized RdmaCommunicator Write flow

Finally, let us talk about the Sync method. Actually it does nothing. In the TCPCommunicator class, the purpose is to flush the output stream used for communication. Since the RDMACommunicator class does not rely on streams, the method is useless and, therefore, empty.

5 Evaluation

Since GVirtuS' main purpose is to allow the leverage of a remote GPU, we decided to deploy the Backend on the HPC Cluster "Purple Jeans" of the University of Naples Parthenope⁴. PurpleJeans is one of the HPC machines available at the Department of Science and Technology of the University of Naples, "Parthenope". It can boast four GPU-accelerated nodes, each sporting four nVidia Tesla V100 GPUs for a total of 16 Tesla V100 GPUs. It certainly is an excellent platform for performing GPGPU virtualization tests. In addition, each node is equipped with Mellanox Infiniband hardware, which is crucial for the tests we are about to perform.

We needed to perform our tests with some CUDA-compatible algorithms. The candidates were a Saxpy algorithm and a Matrix Multiplication algorithm. These two were perfect candidates because they play a crucial role in many numerical computations that underpin Artificial Intelligence computations, and AI makes massive use of GPGPUs to accelerate inference.

The first algorithm we choose is a Saxpy algorithm. Saxpy stands for "Single-Precision A by X plus Y", and it consists in multiplying each element of a vector X by a scalar A and adding the result to the corresponding element in vector Y.

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} + \alpha \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ x_n \end{bmatrix}$$

$$z = ax + y$$

Fig. 8: Saxpy visualization

We implemented it as a CUDA Kernel as described in the nVidia blog⁵.

The second algorithm we choose is a Matrix Multiplication Algorithm. It consists of doing the dot product of the rows of matrix A and the columns of matrix B and putting the resulting scalar in the corresponding entry in the result matrix C.

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_4 & a_5 & a_6 \\ a_7 & a_8 & a_9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_1 & b_2 & b_3 \\ b_4 & b_5 & b_6 \\ b_7 & b_8 & b_9 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & c_2 & c_3 \\ c_4 & c_5 & c_6 \\ c_7 & c_8 & c_9 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n A_{ik} \cdot B_{kj}$$

Fig. 9: Matrix Multiplication visualization

To evaluate the communicators' performance, we used the CUDA events API, which offers a lightweight alternative to CPU timers for performance metrics.

⁴ <https://rcf.uniparthenope.it/it/userguide/>

⁵ <https://developer.nvidia.com/blog/six-ways-saxpy/>

CPU timers require host-device synchronization, stalling the GPU pipeline and invalidating results, making them unsuitable for CUDA metrics. In the NVIDIA blog example, performance was measured using the Saxpy algorithm. However, the measurement was limited to kernel execution time, excluding the crucial host-to-device and device-to-host memory copies. To address this limitation, we made a significant modification to the code. By placing the `cudaEventRecord(start)` call before the host-to-device `cudaMemcpy` and the `cudaEventRecord(stop)` call after the device-to-host `cudaMemcpy`, we were able to capture the full execution time, including these memory operations. This modification was instrumental in our goal to assess the entire execution, providing a more thorough evaluation of GPU performance in GPGPU virtualization.

To assess RDMA’s efficiency in reducing context switches, we compared the voluntary context switches performed by GVirtuS using the TCP-based and RDMA-based Communicators. To achieve this, we used the `/usr/bin/time` command with verbosity.

We used the following setup for our tests: The Backend ran on one of Purple Jeans’ GPU nodes, utilizing one of the four available GPUs. The front end was deployed on the Purple Jeans Frontend node, equipped with an nVidia RTX Quadro 6000, although unused since CUDA function calls were intercepted and offloaded. We evaluated our test programs in five configurations:

- Bare Metal: Programs executed directly on hardware without virtualization.
- TCP/IP Communication: Programs executed via GVirtuS using the TCP communicator over a standard network adapter.
- IP over Infiniband Communication (IPoIB): Programs executed via GVirtuS using the TCP communicator and Infiniband hardware adapters.
- RDMA over Infiniband Communication (unoptimized): Programs executed via GVirtuS using the novel RDMA Communicator without optimizations and with Infiniband hardware.
- RDMA over Infiniband Communication (optimized): Programs executed via GVirtuS using the novel RDMA Communicator with all discussed optimizations and Infiniband hardware.

We chose these setups for specific reasons: Bare Metal evaluation shows performance without virtualization, aiding comparison with virtualized performance and highlighting overhead introduced by GVirtuS. TCP/IP Communicator tests on Ethernet and Infiniband networks demonstrate Infiniband’s impact on transmission speed and serve as a benchmark for the RDMA Communicator. Lastly, we evaluated optimized and unoptimized RDMA Communicator implementations to gauge the impact of optimization and compare them with TCP/IP communicators in Ethernet and IPoIB setups. We conducted multiple executions for each algorithm and setup, and the data we present is the average execution time. Averaging is crucial in virtualization environments where applications typically run for extended periods, prioritizing stability over fluctuations. We’ll report both execution times and the count of voluntary context switches. This metric is insightful as the RDMA Communicator optimizations aim to reduce overhead from excessive context switches, improving performance.

The first test was performed on the Matrix Multiplication Algorithm. We evaluated the performances with the four virtualization setups and the bare metal configuration, and the results are the following:

- **MatrixMul Bare Metal:** 52 milliseconds on average;
- **MatrixMul TCP/IP communication:** 647 milliseconds on average;
- **MatrixMul IPoIB communication:** 439 milliseconds on average;
- **MatrixMul RDMA communication (unoptimized):** 2450 milliseconds on average;
- **MatrixMul RDMA communication (optimized):** 287 milliseconds on average;

We performed multiple executions for each algorithm and setup, presenting the average execution time. Averaging ensures stability in virtualization environments where applications run for extended periods. We will report both execution times and the count of voluntary context switches. This metric is insightful as RDMA Communicator optimizations aim to reduce the overhead from excessive context switches, enhancing performance.

Fig. 10: Matrix Multiplication Algorithm Performances Comparison: best result is achieved with our novel contribution

We already discussed the performance boost that the RDMA Communicator delivers. Now, we demonstrate that reducing the execution times was possible because Infiniband hardware is high-speed and because the RDMA Communicator minimizes the number of the performed context switches. We counted the number of voluntary context switches through the `/usr/bin/time -v` command, and these are the results:

- **MatrixMul TCP/IP communication:** 1016 context switches on average;
- **MatrixMul IPoIB communication:** 956 context switches on average;
- **MatrixMul RDMA communication (unoptimized):** 11788 context switches on average;

Fig. 11: Matrix Multiplication Context Switches: the best result is achieved with our contribution

- **MatrixMul RDMA communication (optimized)**: 105 context switches on average;

This test confirms our hypothesis. The Optimized RDMA Communicator significantly reduces context switches, minimizing kernel overhead. Conversely, the Unoptimized RDMA Communicator incurs high context switches due to frequent memory region registrations. Subsequent sections will demonstrate the performance boost directly linked to context switch reduction.

The SAXPY Algorithm used in this test is more straightforward than the Matrix Multiplication Algorithm we used for the previous tests. The latter performs more `cudaMemcpy` calls, transferring more data between the front and Backend. We will now see that the smaller the program, the smaller the performance boost. The execution times of the SAXPY Algorithm are the following:

- **SAXPY Bare Metal**: 355 milliseconds on average;
- **SAXPY TCP/IP communication**: 2556 milliseconds on average;
- **SAXPY IPoIB communication**: 710 milliseconds on average;
- **SAXPY RDMA communication (unoptimized)**: 499 milliseconds on average;
- **SAXPY RDMA communication (optimized)**: 455 milliseconds on average;

We observed a significant improvement with the Unoptimized RDMA Communicator for the SAXPY Algorithm due to its minimal CUDA call count. Despite the need for numerous system calls to register Memory Regions, the low number of Read and Write calls mitigates context switch overhead, resulting in good performance. The Optimized RDMA Communicator showed an 82% improvement over the TCP/IP Communicator and a 36% improvement over IPoIB communication. However, the boost over the Unoptimized RDMA Communicator was less pronounced, at 8%, due to the reasons mentioned earlier.

Finally, let us look at the context switches that happened during the SAXPY Algorithm’s virtualization. These are the results:

Fig. 12: SAXPY Algorithm Performances Comparison: best result is achieved with our contribution

- **SAXPY TCP/IP communication:** 5884 context switches on average;
- **SAXPY IPoIB communication:** 369 context switches on average;
- **SAXPY RDMA communication (unoptimized):** 325 context switches on average;
- **SAXPY RDMA communication (optimized):** 98 context switches on average;

Fig. 13: SAXPY Context Switches: the best result is achieved with our contribution

We observed a significant decrease in context switches. The poor performance of TCP/IP communication underscores the critical overhead from context switches. TCP/IP communication incurred over sixty times more context switches than the optimized RDMA Communicator, resulting in evident performance disparities.

6 Conclusion

While the novel RDMA Communicator discussed in this work achieved the goal of improving the performances of GVirtuS, it could be better. We optimized the communicator by preregistering the buffer and the associated Memory Region before the communication happens and using a polling-based work completion. Other approaches could further improve the performance of our communicator. We plan to find the best preregistered buffer size in order to always guarantee the fastest send/receive politics, design and test a communicator based on single-sided primitives or a hybrid approach, implement a pipelined solution, implement a buffer cache-alignment, and finally test our novel RDMA Communicator with more algorithms and applications, such as AI Inference and parallel compression/decompression, and implement the needed stub-libraries functions to run these applications.

In any case, our communicator significantly improved the GPGPU remoting performances of GVirtuS. We demonstrated that a performance improvement is possible by reducing the overhead the TCP/IP suite introduces through the numerous memory copies and context switches. Furthermore, we demonstrated that RDMA is a powerful technology. However, its development needs particular attention to detail and wise optimization since our evaluations showed that the Unoptimized RDMA Communicator could be even worse than a traditional TCP Communicator.

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